

Blue-emitting fluorophosphate phosphor to enhance color rendition of near-ultraviolet LED white light

Nguyen Van Dung¹, Nguyen Le Thai², Thuc Minh Bui³, Huu Phuc Dang⁴

¹Faculty of Engineering, Dong Nai Technology University, Bien Hoa City, Vietnam

²Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Nguyen Tat Thanh University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

³Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Nha Trang University, Nha Trang City, Vietnam

⁴Faculty of Fundamental Science, Industrial University of Ho Chi Minh City, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 28, 2023

Revised Nov 30, 2023

Accepted Dec 6, 2023

Keywords:

Blue-emitting phosphor

Light-emitting diodes

$\text{Na}_2\text{MgPO}_4\text{F:Eu}^{2+}$

Phosphors

Spectrum

ABSTRACT

This work presents a novel blue phosphor, $\text{Na}_2\text{MgPO}_4\text{F:Eu}^{2+}$ (NMPF: Eu) for violet 405-nm light-emitting diode (LED) devices. The compound is synthesized via a simple one-step sintering process using readily available precursors. Notably, NMPF: Eu exhibits highly efficient and thermally stable blue emission when excited by violet light. The NMPF: Eu is applied to produce a white LED device driven by a 405 nm LED chip and $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}\text{:Ce}^{3+}$ (YAG: Ce) yellow phosphor. The impacts of NMPF: Eu phosphors are investigated by varying their particle size while maintaining consistent doping concentrations. Impressively, the LED prototype displays a substantial reduction in blue light emission while generating white light with enhanced color rendering and luminous properties. These results highlight the suitability and potential of NMPF: Eu as a promising phosphor for widening violet LED applications, especially in generating white light perceptible to the human eyes.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Huu Phuc Dang

Faculty of Fundamental Science, Industrial University of Ho Chi Minh City

No. 12 Nguyen Van Bao Street, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Email: danghuuphuc@iuh.edu.vn

1. INTRODUCTION

The continuous advancement of energy-efficient lighting technologies has led to the widespread adoption of light-emitting diode (LED) lights for various applications, such as general illumination, displays, and automotive lighting [1]–[3]. To achieve high-quality white light, LEDs often employ phosphor materials to convert part of their emission spectrum to complementary colors, typically blue light excitation to yellow or red-light emission. One of the most current ways to achieve the efficient white light for LED lighting systems is the utilization of InGaN blue-emitting LED chips combined with the yellow-emitting $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}\text{:Ce}^{3+}$ phosphor (YAG: Ce). However, this type of LED device is reported with low color rendering efficiency and cool white light owing to the intense blue-light emission [4].

Achieving a reduction in LED-chip blue emission intensity can be accomplished through a viable approach involves employing the combination of phosphor materials of blue, red, and green emissions and a 405-nm violet LED chip. The violet-LED generated white light exhibits improved color rendering index (CRI) and lumen performance compared to that from traditional blue-LED packages. Additionally, it reduces the likelihood of droop, enhancing overall LED performance. Furthermore, employing violet LEDs enables the covering over the near-ultraviolet (UV) and blue regions, creating a continuous and broader emission spectrum to improve the chromatic tunability [5], [6]. Nonetheless, under the violet excitation of 405 nm, the phosphor must exhibit a high photoluminescent quantum yield to address the Stokes' loss issue. Moreover,

the phosphors must demonstrate emission intensity degradation and chromaticity drift due to variations in temperature to deliver a consistent emission color perceptible to the average human eye.

Many studies have investigated and proposed potential green and red phosphors satisfying the posing requirements but analysis on effective phosphor under a 405-nm excitation is barely conducted. The most common blue phosphor in the market is BaMgAl₁₀O₁₇: Eu²⁺ phosphor. This phosphor was reported to exhibit efficiently high quantum yield under the 400-nm violet LED, making it suitable for plasma display technologies and domestic illumination. However, one significant limitation of BaMgAl₁₀O₁₇: Eu²⁺ lies in its susceptibility to hydrolysis, leading to the rare-earth ionic oxidation from Eu²⁺ to Eu³⁺. Consequently, prolonged operation of this phosphor results in observable shifts in the emission wavelength and a subsequent decrease in emission intensity. While alternative blue phosphors like Sr₃MgSi₂O₈: Eu²⁺ (SMS: Eu) and Ca₅(PO₄)₃Cl: Eu²⁺ (CPC: Eu) exhibit strong absorption in the violet region, they suffer from specific shortcomings. Particularly, the SMS: Eu phosphor demonstrates poor thermal stability, and the CPC: Eu experiences reduced efficiency, making them less suitable alternatives in practical applications [7]–[10].

In this research paper, we report a novel blue phosphor Na₂MgPO₄F: Eu²⁺ (NMPF: Eu) that is well excited by violet LED chips. The synthesis of this compound involves a one-step sintering process using available precursors. A key feature of this phosphor is its high blue-emission efficiency and stability under violet illumination excitation. We demonstrated the application of NMPF: Eu in a LED device pumped by a 405 nm LED chip, resulting in the generation of white light with improved chroma rendering efficiency. The impacts of NMPF: Eu phosphors are monitored by varying its particle size while keeping its doping concentration fixed. Remarkably, the device exhibited enhanced color rendering properties with high luminosity with the utilization of bigger NMPF: Eu particle sizes. Collectively, these findings underscore the efficiency of the NMPF: Eu phosphors for the development of violet LED devices.

2. METHOD

The NMPF: Eu phosphor was produced using the solid phase reaction process with high purity (>99.9%) reacting agents. The specific elements and their origins are shown in Table 1. To start the synthesis, all reagents were blended stoichiometrically in an acetone medium by grinding in an agate mortar. The doping concentration of Eu was at 0.04 mol% and Na₂CO₃ was added with an additional amount of 7.5 wt%. This addition contributes to compensating for the evaporation during synthesis [11], [12]. Then, the initially mixed compound was subjected to a ball-milling grinding process for 100 minutes. The resulting powder was subsequently pressed into a pellet with a radius of 3 mm. Next, the pellet was put in the alumina crucible and the sintering process was carried out at 825°C for 8 hours in a reduced atmosphere (5% H₂: 95% N₂). Afterward, the heated pellet was re-ground for further examinations. The luminescence of the NMPF: Eu phosphor and the produced white LED were collected using the instruments listed in Table 2.

Table 1. Eu²⁺-doped Na₂MgPO₄F starting reagents

Reacting components	Bought from
Na ₂ CO ₃	Sigma Aldrich
MgF ₂	Sigma Aldrich
MgO	Sigma Aldrich
NH ₄ H ₂ PO ₄	Acros Organics
Eu ₂ O ₃	Alfa Aesar

Table 2. Luminescence determining tools

Characteristics	Tools
Phosphor luminescent spectrum	Horiba Fluoromax-4 fluorescence spectrophotometer (excitation source of a 150-W xenon lamp)
Temperature-dependent emission spectrum	PTI fluorescence spectrophotometer (excitation source of a 75-W xenon lamp) with a Janis VPF-100 cryostat for an 80-640 K temperature-controlled environment
Quantum yield	Labsphere spectralon-coated 150-mm-diameter integrating sphere and de Mello et al's method
LED luminous spectrum and performance	Avasphere-5-IRRAD spectrophotometer

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The NMPF adopts an orthorhombic crystal structure, classified under the Pbcn (No. 60) space group. Its structure is characterized by a robust and tightly interconnected backbone composed of NMPF units. Within this intricate unit, two crystallographically independent NaO₅F₂ polyhedra, centered on Na atoms, share faces with two highly distorted MgO₄F₂ octahedra [13]. Despite the isovalency between

Eu^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , it is anticipated that Eu^{2+} ions will substitute for one or both of the Na^+ ions. This expectation arises from the fact that the ionic radius of Eu^{2+} closely matches that of Na^+ , in contrast to Mg^{2+} [14]. This ionic substitution in the NMPF: Eu structure can contribute to the generation of blue light under the UV illumination. The excitation spectrum of the NMPF: Eu phosphor reveals notable peaks at approximately 340, 365, and 400 nm. Generally, the excitation peaks at around 340 nm and 365 nm are common with blue-emitting phosphors, but the NMPF: Eu phosphor shows ability to be excited at 400 nm, resulting in the production of blue light with a uniquely short Stokes' shift. Consequently, the blue-emission minimization can be achieved for LED light, especially crucial for the LED applications focus on producing warm white light for human-visual comfort at night [15].

When using the NMPF: Eu phosphor in the LED fabrication, its particle size is altered, inducing the changes in the scattering factor of the package. We determined the scattering of light at different wavelengths from 380 nm to 780 nm and demonstrated the result in Figure 1. All wavelengths show increased scattering performance, both reduced scattering and scattering coefficients, in response to the enlargement of NMPF: Eu particle diameter. Moreover, the UV (380 nm) show the highest reduced scattering coefficients, indicating the higher UV-light utilization by the phosphor with large diameter. The improved scattering efficiency on the increasing NMPF: Eu particle size also contribute to induce the excitation light absorption effectiveness and re-emitted light scattering by the phosphor materials in the package. As a result, the color dispersion and reproduction can be enhanced.

Figure 1. The scattering efficiency in the LED with different NMPF: Eu diameters from 1 μm to 20 μm

During the operation of the LED devices, the heat increase is unavoidable, which affects the color coordination. In an increasing temperature environment, from 300 K to 500 K, the NMPF: Eu phosphor exhibited a blue shift, attributed to the intensified higher energy peak and the low energy peak's quenching at elevated temperatures. Therefore, the NMPF: Eu phosphor proves to have remarkable chromatic stability within the typical examined temperature range in an LED device. This indicates that using the NMPF: Eu phosphor can improve the chromatic uniformity of the LED package [16].

The correlated color temperature (CCT) range and CCT delta assessments were carried out with different sizes of NMPF: Eu phosphor particles. The results are depicted in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. Overall, increasing the particle size of NMPF: Eu does not absolutely benefit the color uniformity as this somewhat induces the CCT delta, the average difference between the highest CCT and lowest CCT points of an angular CCT range. There is a notable fluctuation in CCT ranges of the LED when increasing the particle size of NMPF: Eu phosphor. When increasing the NMPF: Eu particle size an increment from 1 μm to 2 μm , the CCT delta bottoms out with a value of ~ 25 K. This means the color difference on the chroma scale is insignificant, resulting in the more satisfying color uniformity. As the NMPF: Eu particle size increases, the CCT delta also increases and peaks at ~ 225 K when NMPF: Eu diameter is 7 μm . Continuing enlarging the demonstrates a significant drop in CCT delta, but the values are still higher compared to that obtained with 2 μm NMPF: Eu particles. So, to achieve the best color uniformity, using the NMPF: Eu phosphor with a particle size of 2 μm seems to be an ideal option.

Figure 2. Angular CCT range of the LED emission with different NMPF: Eu diameters from 1 μm to 20 μm

Figure 3. CCT delta of the LED emission with different NMPF: Eu diameters from 1 μm to 20 μm

The fluctuation and increased CCT delta could be ascribed to the changes in the transmission peak intensity as a function of altering NMPF: Eu diameters. The transmission peaks of the LED with different NMPF: Eu diameters from 1 μm to 20 μm are displayed in Figure 4. The difference when increasing the NMPF: Eu diameter from 1 μm to 2 μm is noticeable, especially in the region of 550-635 nm. With the particle size larger than 2 μm, the peak intensity does not alter much. Besides, the peak at 590 nm (yellow) is much more intense than that at the 450 nm (blue). This result indicate that the converted yellow light power is stronger than the blue one. The change in YAG: Ce concentration on the increasing NMPF: Eu granule diameters, shown in Figure 5, can demonstrate this phenomenon. When the bigger NMPF: Eu particles are added, given that the NMPF: Eu concentration is fixed, the concentration of YAG: Ce yellow phosphor increases. The highest of YAG: Ce amounts are recorded when NMPF: Eu particle size ranges from 5-7 μm. With NMPF: Eu particles larger than 7 μm, the YAG: Ce concentration slightly declines but is greater than that with 1-2 μm NMPF: Eu particles. The increase in YAG: Ce amounts promote its absorption and conversion of blue light emitted from NMPF: Eu particles, leading to the notable intensity in transmission power [17].

The luminous flux of the LED as a function of altering the NMPF: Eu diameters is subsequently shown in Figure 6. The increasing NMPF: Eu diameters is beneficial to the luminosity of the white LED, according from the demonstrated data. The luminous intensity gradually increases with the NMPF: Eu particle-size enlargement, reaching its peak when NMPF: Eu particle size is 10 μm. The decline in luminosity is also noticed with the diameter more than 10 μm, but the intensity is far more significant compared to the result in the case of 1 μm NMPF: Eu particle size. Notably, with larger particle sizes, the light transformation between blue and yellow or red-orange is amplified, owing to the broader phosphor sheet associated with larger particles. Consequently, the overall spectral energy decreases. Moreover, in the case of substantial particle size, the transformed light may experience rear-reflection, leading to a reduction in luminescent intensity and an increase in the CCT level [18].

Figure 4. Transmission spectral power of the LED emission with different NMPF: Eu diameters (1-20 μm)

Figure 5. YAG: Ce of the LED emission with different NMPF: Eu diameters from 1 μm to 20 μm

Figure 6. Luminous flux of the LED emission with different NMPF: Eu diameters from 1 μm to 20 μm

To evaluate how illumination conveys hues to our visual perception, the CRI has traditionally been employed, assessing illumination based on sunlight standards. While CRI has served as a longstanding indicator of hue quality and is suitable for older lighting technologies like incandescent and fluorescent lights, its limited coverage of only eight hue samples makes it inadequate for modern devices, especially LEDs, which encompass a broader range of hues. Consequently, CRI cannot accurately evaluate the chromatic performance of LED devices. To address this limitation, a more comprehensive index called the color quality scale (CQS) was introduced [19]–[21]. Unlike its predecessor, CQS incorporates multiple variations in chromatic quality, encompassing aspects such as hue, brightness, and saturation, enabling a more inclusive assessment of hue output. With these additional factors considered, CQS emerges as a much more appropriate and reliable index for evaluating light quality in white LED devices.

The resulted CRI and CQS in connection to the NMPF: Eu diameters of 1–20 μm are presented in Figures 7 and 8. Increasing the NMPF: Eu diameters generally promotes the rendering performance of the LED white light. The CRI increases when the NMPF: Eu diameter is enlarged from 1 μm to 2 μm. After that, the values remain quite stable regardless of using bigger NMPF: Eu particles. In terms of the CQS, the enhancement with larger NMPF: Eu particles is more notable. With the utilization of 13 μm NMPF: Eu particles, the best CQS value is obtained. The CQS value recorded in the case of 9 μm NMPF: Eu particles is in the second place, which is slightly lower than the peak. The notable CQS values with such NMPF: Eu particle sizes can be attributed to the increase CRIs and the better color coordination (low CCT delta). Thus, the larger NMPF: Eu particles can be applied to enhance the color rendering efficiency of the white LED package [22]–[25].

Figure 7. CRI performance of the LED emission with different NMPF: Eu diameters from 1 μm to 20 μm

Figure 8. CQS performance of the LED emission with different NMPF: Eu diameters from 1 μm to 20 μm

4. CONCLUSION

This research introduces a novel blue phosphor, NMPF: Eu, specifically designed for violet 405 nm LED devices. The compound is synthesized through a one-step sintering solid-state reaction. Significantly, NMPF: Eu demonstrates highly efficient and thermally stable blue emission under violet light excitation. We developed a white LED device by combining this phosphor with a 405 nm LED chip and YAG: Ce yellow phosphor. Through a comprehensive investigation, we explored the impacts of varying NMPF: Eu phosphor particle sizes. The increasing phosphor particle size resulting in stronger scattering performance, enabling the improvement of CRI, CQS and luminous properties. Besides, the blue emission intensity within the white light range is lower than that of the yellow emission owing to the higher concentration of YAG: Ce phosphor, leading greater blue-light utilization by the yellow phosphor. These outcomes underscore the remarkable suitability and potential of NMPF: Eu as a promising phosphor for expanding violet LED applications. This research contributes to the advancement of energy-efficient LED lighting technology and opens new avenues for its practical implementation in various lighting scenarios.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. C. A. Rashid *et al.*, "Spectrophotometer with enhanced sensitivity for uric acid detection," *Chinese Optics Letters*, vol. 17, no. 8, p. 081701, 2019, doi: 10.3788/col201917.081701.
- [2] W. Rui, D. Jing-yuan, S. An-cun, W. Yong-jie, and L. Yu-liang, "Indoor optical wireless communication system utilizing white LED lights," in *2009 15th Asia-Pacific Conference on Communications*, IEEE, Oct. 2009, pp. 617–621, doi: 10.1109/APCC.2009.5375555.
- [3] H. Zhao, C. Chen, and S. W. R. Lee, "Effects of GaN blue LED chip and phosphor on optical performance of white light LED," in *2012 2nd IEEE CPMT Symposium Japan*, IEEE, Dec. 2012, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ICSJ.2012.6523414.
- [4] K. Richter, S. Aleksic, and C. A. Bunge, "Estimating the modulation characteristics of white leds by their color temperature," in *2018 20th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON)*, IEEE, Jul. 2018, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ICTON.2018.8473805.
- [5] F. J. Lopez-Hernandez, E. Poves, R. Perez-Jimenez, and J. Rabadan, "Low-cost diffuse wireless optical communication system based on white LED," *Proceedings of the International Symposium on Consumer Electronics, ISCE*, pp. 19–22, 2006, doi: 10.1109/isce.2006.1689461.

- [6] K. H. Loo, Y. M. Lai, and C. K. Tse, "A low-cost method for minimizing the chromaticity shift of dc-driven phosphor-converted white LEDs by thermal design," in *8th International Conference on Power Electronics - ECCE Asia*, IEEE, May 2011, pp. 515–519, doi: 10.1109/ICPE.2011.5944595.
- [7] J. Wang, Z. Kang, and N. Zou, "Research on indoor visible light communication system employing white LED lightings," in *IET International Conference on Communication Technology and Application (ICCTA 2011)*, IET, 2011, pp. 934–937, doi: 10.1049/cp.2011.0807.
- [8] X. Zhang, Y. Peng, J. Li, and T. Shi, "Opto-thermal performances investigation of phosphor-in-glass based chip-scale white LEDs," in *2022 23rd International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology (ICEPT)*, IEEE, Aug. 2022, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ICEPT56209.2022.9873334.
- [9] S. Fujita, A. Sakamoto, and S. Tanabe, "Luminescence characteristics of YAG glass-ceramic phosphor for white LED," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 1387–1391, 2008, doi: 10.1109/JSTQE.2008.920285.
- [10] A. M. Muslu and M. Arik, "Impact of electronics over localized hot spots in multi-chip white LED light engines," in *2019 18th IEEE Intersociety Conference on Thermal and Thermomechanical Phenomena in Electronic Systems (ITHERM)*, IEEE, May 2019, pp. 31–39, doi: 10.1109/ITHERM.2019.8757383.
- [11] J. Sun, Y. Peng, H. Zheng, X. Guo, Z. Gan, and S. Liu, "Enhancing ACU of white LEDs by phosphor coating based on electrohydrodynamics," *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 393–396, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1109/LPT.2017.2651044.
- [12] F. M. Wu, C. T. Lin, C. C. Wei, C. W. Chen, H. T. Huang, and C. H. Ho, "1.1-Gb/s white-led-based visible light communication employing carrier-less amplitude and phase modulation," *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 24, no. 19, pp. 1730–1732, Oct. 2012, doi: 10.1109/LPT.2012.2210540.
- [13] C. H. Chiang, S. J. Gong, T. S. Zhan, K.-C. Cheng, and S. Y. Chu, "White light-emitting diodes with high color rendering index and tunable color temperature fabricated using separated phosphor layer structure," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 898–901, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1109/LED.2016.2576498.
- [14] E. Setiawan, T. Adiono, I. N. O. Osahon, and W. O. Popoola, "Experimental demonstration of visible light communication using white LED, blue filter and soc based test-bed," in *2019 International Symposium on Electronics and Smart Devices (ISESD)*, IEEE, Oct. 2019, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ISESD.2019.8909625.
- [15] J. Song, W. Zhang, L. Zhou, X. Zhou, J. Sun, and C.-X. Wang, "A new light source of VLC combining white LEDs and RGB LEDs," in *2017 IEEE/CIC International Conference on Communications in China (ICCC)*, IEEE, Oct. 2017, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICCCChina.2017.8330369.
- [16] J. Zhou and W. Yan, "Experimental investigation on the performance characteristics of white LEDs used in illumination application," in *2007 IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference*, IEEE, 2007, pp. 1436–1440, doi: 10.1109/PESC.2007.4342205.
- [17] K. J. Chen *et al.*, "Efficiency and droop improvement in hybrid warm white LEDs using InGaN and AlGaInP high-voltage LEDs," *Journal of Display Technology*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 280–284, Apr. 2013, doi: 10.1109/JDT.2012.2227054.
- [18] T. Komine and M. Nakagawa, "Performance evaluation of visible-light wireless communication system using white LED lightings," in *Proceedings. ISCC 2004. Ninth International Symposium on Computers And Communications (IEEE Cat. No.04TH8769)*, IEEE, pp. 258–263, doi: 10.1109/ISCC.2004.1358414.
- [19] S. Zong, J. Wu, and X. He, "A novel method for illumination and communication using white LED lights," in *6th IET International Conference on Power Electronics, Machines and Drives (PEMD 2012)*, IET, 2012, pp. P70–P70, doi: 10.1049/cp.2012.0149.
- [20] L. Rakotomalala, Z. Randriamanantany, S. Hartopan, R. Hertanu, and D. D. Lucache, "Variance of radiometric performances for cool-white and neutral-white LED luminaries," in *2016 International Conference and Exposition on Electrical and Power Engineering (EPE)*, IEEE, Oct. 2016, pp. 520–524, doi: 10.1109/ICEPE.2016.7781394.
- [21] J.-X. Li, J. L. Zheng, X. W. Du, Z. T. Li, and J. S. Li, "Enhancement of optical performance for quantum dot white LEDs with semi-spherical lens packaging structure using SiO₂ nanoparticles," in *2019 20th International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology (ICEPT)*, IEEE, Aug. 2019, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ICEPT47577.2019.245159.
- [22] T. Komine and M. Nakagawa, "Integrated system of white LED visible-light communication and power-line communication," in *The 13th IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications*, IEEE, pp. 1762–1766, doi: 10.1109/PIMRC.2002.1045482.
- [23] F. Zhao, G. Dong, G. Yang, Y. Zeng, B. Shieh, and S. W. R. Lee, "Study on light emitting surface temperature of LEDs," in *2020 21st International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology (ICEPT)*, IEEE, Aug. 2020, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/ICEPT50128.2020.9202667.
- [24] F. Wu, W. Zhao, S. Yang, and C. Zhang, "Failure modes and failure analysis of white LEDs," in *2009 9th International Conference on Electronic Measurement & Instruments*, IEEE, Aug. 2009, pp. 4-978-4-981, doi: 10.1109/ICEMI.2009.5274756.
- [25] C. Shen, K. Li, Q. Hou, H. Feng, and X. Dong, "White LED based on YAG : Ce,Gd phosphor and CdSe-ZnS core/shell quantum dots," *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 22, no. 12, pp. 884–886, Jun. 2010, doi: 10.1109/LPT.2010.2046724.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nguyen Van Dung received a Master's degree in mechanical engineering from the Ho Chi Minh University of Technology and Education, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, and is currently working as a lecturer at the Faculty of Engineering, Dong Nai Technology University, Bien Hoa City, Vietnam. His research interests include system optimization techniques, simulation and modeling, machine design, mold design. He can be contacted at email: nguyenvandung@dntu.edu.vn.

Nguyen Le Thai received his B.S. in Electronic engineering from Danang University of Science and Technology, Vietnam, in 2003, M.S. in Electronic Engineering from Posts and Telecommunications Institute of Technology, Ho Chi Minh, Vietnam, in 2011 and Ph.D. degree of Mechatronics Engineering from Kunming University of Science and Technology, China, in 2016. He is currently with the Nguyen Tat Thanh University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. His research interests include the renewable energy, optimisation techniques, robust adaptive control and signal processing. He can be contacted at email: nlthai@ntt.edu.vn.

Thuc Minh Bui got his B.S. and M.S. degrees in Electrical Engineering from Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology and Education in 2005 and 2008, respectively, and his Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering at from Yeungnam University in Gyeongsan, Korea, in 2018. He is currently a lecturer at the Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering at Nha Trang University in Nha Trang City, Vietnam. His scientific interests include control theory, power converter, automation, and optical science with applications to industry and the environment. He can be contacted at email: minhbt@ntu.edu.vn.

Huu Phuc Dang received a Physics Ph.D. degree from the University of Science, Ho Chi Minh City, in 2018. Currently, he is a lecturer at the Faculty of Fundamental Science, Industrial University of Ho Chi Minh City, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. His research interests include simulation LEDs material, renewable energy. He can be contacted at email: danghuuphuc@iuh.edu.vn.